

Advanced experiences of Eastern thinkers on raising a mature generation

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Annotation: In this article, Eastern thinkers, their famous ideas about education, their role in the development of a perfect person, and their researches are mentioned.

Key words: Eastern thinkers, Education, perfect personality, perfect personality education

On June 15, 2019, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev visited the area where the Center of Islamic Civilization of Uzbekistan will be built and laid the foundation stone. Today, building constructions are rising and construction works are going on rapidly.

The head of our state pays special attention to restoring our national and religious values and promoting the great contribution of our great ancestors to the development of Islam.

Abu Rayhan Beruni was one of the first in the history of mankind to express the opinion that teaching children to work from an early age, raising them to respect the work of adults, and teaching children to science and profession should be the

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focus of the family. Alloma emphasized that it is necessary to continue the education of work that started in the family, connecting it with education at school and teaching a trade. The great thinker carefully studied the inheritance of work and profession from generation to generation based on inheritance, and he highly valued the craft activities of people¹. It is self-evident that, while demanding hard work and in-depth knowledge, this activity created the basis for the wide spread of inventiveness among craftsmen. Abu Rayhan Beruni was one of the first in the history of mankind to express the opinion that teaching children to work from an early age, raising them to respect the work of adults, and teaching children to science and profession should be the focus of the family. Alloma emphasized that it is necessary to continue the education of work that started in the family, connecting it with education at school and teaching a trade. The great thinker carefully studied the inheritance of work and profession from generation to generation based on inheritance, and he highly valued the craft activities of people¹. It is self-evident that, while demanding hard work and in-depth knowledge, this activity created the basis for the wide spread of inventiveness among craftsmen.

Kaikovus mentions the importance of knowledge and intelligence and puts it above wealth. "If you are poor because of lack of wealth, try to become rich with your mind, because it is better to be rich with your mind than to be rich with your possessions. the mind cannot be learned. Bilgil concludes that intelligence is a commodity that cannot be stolen, it does not burn in fire, it does not flow in water, and human manners are also a sign of intelligence, i.e. al adab - suratil aql.

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Mahmud Kashgari in his work "Devoni Lugatit Turk" "Listen to the words of knowledgeable and intelligent people with kindness. Learn the sciences and crafts and implement them," he says. Alloma's opinion encourages people to work and do good and condemns evil. He honors the masters of knowledge and crafts and calls people to learn from them. The entrepreneur Amir Temur further developed such industries as handicrafts - textile, wood and stone carving, carpet weaving, ceramic and metal products manufacturing, which became an independent industry on the basis of a large division of labor in his kingdom, as well as agriculture, He paid great attention to cattle breeding and trade. Because of this, an opportunity was created for the emergence of new professions in social life, mass unemployment was not allowed. Ajd Mahmud Kashgari in "Devoni lugatit turk" "Listen to the words of knowledgeable and intelligent people with kindness." Learn the sciences and crafts and implement them," he says.

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Pedagogical conditions for the formation of good qualities in young people were determined with the help of the works of Eastern thinkers.

Describing the image of a mature person enlightened by his knowledge, Farabi says: "Whoever says that he has not learned wisdom, let him start at a young age, let him be healthy, have good morals and manners, let him succeed in his words. , be protected from bad deeds, know all laws and regulations, be knowledgeable and eloquent, respect learned and wise people, do not spare the world of knowledge and people of knowledge, have knowledge about all real material things Let's go."

In conclusion, I would like to say that at the present time, the development of society cannot be achieved without the intellectual and spiritual development of the young generation. In this regard, it has been scientifically proven that the social teachings of Central Asian thinkers are of great importance. Social Thoughts in the development of the social teaching of thinkers in Central Asia, their thoughts and ideas on the education of students' spiritual qualities are based on the requirements of the development of the society of their time, and in the following periods, intelligence, knowledge, creativity, creativity, behavior in the education of the young generation. based on the fact that manners, human relations, hard work, and a healthy lifestyle have not lost their importance in creating content

From the first years of independence, there was a great need to reform the fields of education, science, and vocational training at the level of the whole country. It should be noted that enlightenment is in the blood of our people and nation. According to the traditional oriental view, enlightenment is not only knowledge and skills, but also deep spirituality and good morals.

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